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New finding of *Stathmopoda ficivora* Kasy, 1973 in Iran (Lepidoptera, Gelechioidea: Stathmopodidae)

Helen Alipanah

Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection (IRIPP), Agricultural Research, Education and Extension Organization (AREEO), Tehran.

ABSTRACT. *Stathmopoda ficivora* Kasy was identified based on a female specimen collected in the late of June 2013 in Dorbadam protected area, N. Ghuchan, Khorasan-e Razavi Province. This species is newly reported for the fauna of Iran. A brief taxonomic characterization of the species is provided and the examined adult female and its genitalia are figured.

Key words: Gelechioidea, Stathmopodidae, *S. ficivora*, Iran, new record

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Introduction

The family Stathmopodidae contains small to medium-sized moths that can be recognized by the very peculiar position of most species on the leaves of their host plants, with hind legs stretched along the sides of the body or even raised above it. The narrow and very pointed wings with very long fringes, peculiarly armed hind legs and typical morphology of the genital duct in the female, are main diagnostic characters of the family. They are mostly distributed in Indo-Australian and Afrotropical regions, with very few representatives in the Neotropical and the temperate zones of the Holarctic region. Over 350 species of this family have been described all around the world (Sinev, 2015). More than 20 species are known from the Palearctic region and are mainly occurring in its extreme south and south-

eastern parts (Koster & Sinev, 2003; Koster, 2010).

As far as our knowledge goes, only four species namely, *Tortilia flavella* Chrétien, 1908, *T. palidella* Kasy, 1973, *Stathmopoda auriferella* (Walker, 1864), and *S. diplaspis* (Meyrick, 1887) are known for this family in Iran. These species were collected in Tehran, Bandar Abbas, Bandar Abbas, and Tehran, respectively, of which, *T. palidella* is described from Iran (Kasy, 1973).

In late June 2013, a female *Stathmopoda* Herrich-Schäffer, 1853 specimen was collected in the north of Ghuchan, Khorasan-e Razavi Province which was externally different from the two previously reported species of the genus from Iran. The specimen was dissected and identified as *S.*

Corresponding author: Helen Alipanah, E-mail: halipanah@gmail.com

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ficivora Kasy, 1973. The type specimens of this species have been collected in Kara Kala, Turkmenistan (Kasy, 1973) which is close to the collecting area of *S. ficivora* in Iran. This species is newly reported for the fauna of Iran. The genus *Stathmopoda* has a worldwide distribution mainly in tropical and subtropical areas (Koster & Sinev, 2003; Sinev, 2015).

Material and methods

The genitalia dissection followed Robinson (1976). Photographs were taken using a digital Still camera DSC-F717 and a Dino-Eye Microscope Eye-piece camera. The examined specimen collected at light. It is deposited in the Hayk Mirzayans Insect Museum (HMIM), Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection (IRIPP).

Results

The adult examined female specimen and its genitalia are briefly characterized as follows:

Stathmopoda ficivora Kasy, 1973 (Fig. 1A)

Material examined: Iran, Khorāsān-e Razavi Prov.: 1♀, Ghuchān-Bājgirān Rd., 46 km. N. Ghuchān, Dorbādām protected area, N 37° 25' 25.5", E 058° 31' 34", 1800 m, 20.vi.2013, Ālipanāh, Falsafi leg. (GS: HA-2336).

Diagnosis: Wingspan 11.8–13.0 mm (Kasy, 1973); however wingspan of the examined female 15.0 mm and its forewing length 7.5 mm (Fig. 1A); antennae shining dirty-cream; thorax shining dark yellow with a medial broad band, and gray posteriorly; forewing very narrow, shining gray with a very small pale yellow basal spot, an irregular dark yellow spot at one-sixth narrowing distally, and irregularly edged pale yellow spot in the middle (Kasy, 1973) which is slightly narrower than the latter spot, apex of the forewing at distal one-fifth dark yellow; fringes shining, light-brownish-gray. Hindwing brownish-gray, slightly brighter at base, fringes in the same color as the hindwing and shining.

In the genitalia of examined female (Figs 1B–D) corpus bursae with two unequal-sized signa: A relatively long signum which is widened in the middle part and narrowed at distal ends, with a pointed sclerotized process beyond the middle giving it a broken appearance. Small weakly sclerotized plates present around the longer signum in the middle (Figs 1B, C). Another signum the shorter and despite that of Kasy (1973), with tiny spines around, which are mainly concentrated in one part. Width of the shorter signum gradually increases towards the middle part (Figs 1B, D). The thorns on the basal part of the tubular portion of corpus bursae does not arranged in distinct rows, and a peculiar elongated sclerotized plate present at the back of the tubular area.

Distribution: Turkmenistan (Kara-Kala) Nigeria, Namibia, South Africa and probably other areas of Africa and southwest Asia (Kasy, 1973; Sinev, 1988, 2004), United Arab Emirates (Koster, 2010), and Iran (Khorasan-e Razavi Province).

Remarks: The larvae live on the fruits of fig (*Ficus carica* L.) (Krasilnikova, 1989) and can be harmful (Kasy, 1973), but the host plant of this species in Iran is unknown.

Discussion

The genus *Stathmopoda* is one of the agriculture and forestry pest groups in the world (Kim et al., 2017); although the host plant of *S. ficivora* in Iran was unknown and nothing found regarding to those of the remaining two species occurring in Iran. Only three specimens belonging to two species, i.e., *S. ficivora* and *S. diplaspis* were found in HMIM, surprisingly. This may indicate their weak attraction to light traps or their low populations in Iran.

Figure 1. *Stathmopoda ficivora* Kasy, **A.** Adult female; **B.** Female genitalia (main body in ventral view); **C.** Longer signum; **D.** Shorter signum.

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Conflict of Interests

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

- Kasy, F. (1973) Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Familie Stathmopodidae Meyrick, 1913 (Lepidoptera, Gelechioidea). *Tijdschrift voor Entomologie*, 116 (13), 227–299.
- Koster, J.C. (2010) Order Lepidoptera, family Stathmopodidae. In: A. van Harten (Ed.), *Arthropod fauna of the UAE*, 3(30), 519–524. Dar Al Ummah Printing, Publishing & Advertising, Abu Dhabi, UAE.
- Koster, J.C. & Sinev, S.Yu. (2003) Momphidae, Batrachedridae, Stathmopodidae, Agonoxenidae, Cosmopterigidae, Chrysopeleiiidae. In: Huemer, P., Karsholt, O. & Lyneborg, L. (Eds), *Microlepidoptera of Europe*, Volume 5, 1–387. Apollo Books, Stenstrup, Denmark.
- Kim, S., Lee, W. & Lee, S. (2017) Estimation of a new molecular marker of the genus *Stathmopoda* (Lepidoptera: Stathmopodidae): Comparing EF1a and COI sequences. *Journal of Asia-Pacific Entomology*, 20(1), 269–280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aspen.2016.12.002>
- Krasilnikova, G.A. (1989) Morphology and ecology of the fig bright-legged moth *Stathmopoda ficivora* (Lepidoptera, Stathmopodidae). *Vestnik Zoologii*, (6), 79–81.
- Robinson, G.S. (1976) The preparation of slides of Lepidoptera genitalia with special reference to the Microlepidoptera. *Entomologist's Gazette*, 27, 127–132.
- Sinev, S.Yu. (1988) A review of bright-legged moths (Lepidoptera, Stathmopodidae) in the fauna of the USSR. *Proceedings of the Zoological Institute, Leningrad*, 178, 104–133.
- Sinev, S.Yu. (2004) Agonoxenidae, Blastobasidae, Chrysopeleiiidae, Cosmopterigidae and Stathmopodidae (Lepidoptera: Gelechioidea). In: W. Mey (Ed.), *The Lepidoptera of the Brandenburg Massif in Namibia*. *Esperiana Memoir*, 1, 107–130.
- Sinev, S.Yu. (2015) *World catalogue of bright-legged moths (Lepidoptera, Stathmopodidae)*. St. Petersburg: ZIN RAS. 84 pp.

گزارش گونه *Stathmopoda ficivora* Kasy, 1973 (Lepidoptera: Gelechioidea: Stathmopodidae) برای اولین بار از ایران

هلن عالی پناه

مؤسسه تحقیقات گیاه پزشکی کشور، سازمان تحقیقات، آموزش و ترویج کشاورزی، صندوق پستی ۱۴۵۴-۱۹۳۹۵، تهران.
* پست الکترونیکی نویسنده مسئول مکاتبه: halipannah@gmail.com
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چکیده: گونه *Stathmopoda ficivora* Kasy بر مبنای یک نمونه ماده که در اواخر خردادماه سال ۱۳۹۳ از منطقه حفاظت شده دربادام در شمال قوچان (استان خراسان رضوی) جمع آوری شده است، شناسایی شد. این گونه برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می شود. در این مقاله، گونه مزبور به اختصار معرفی شده و تصویر خصوصیات افتراقی نمونه مورد مطالعه ارائه شده است.

واژگان کلیدی: *Stathmopoda ficivora*, Stathmopodidae, Gelechioidea, گزارش جدید، ایران